

BWR Whole Core Neutronics/Thermal-Hydraulics Coupling Simulation Using Multi-Physics Platform JAMPAN

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ABSTRACT

High-fidelity multi-physics simulations are important for the verification of core design codes. JAEA is developing a high-fidelity multi-physics platform JAMPAN to couple many single-physics codes. This platform consists of the HDF5-formatted original data container and input/output data handler modules to generate input files and read output files for coupling single-physics codes. The target calculation scale of this platform is the whole core and single assembly geometries. Users can easily change the calculation code depending on their target scale. For example, users can use the subchannel thermal hydraulics code for a whole core geometry and the computational fluid dynamics code for a single assembly geometry. This paper demonstrates the BWR whole core neutronics and thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation using the continuous energy Monte Carlo calculation code MVP and the three-field subchannel code NASCA. The initial loading core of Peach Bottom Unit 2 obtained from the OECD/NEA Peach Bottom turbine trip benchmark was used for the BWR core calculations. The k-effective value and the axial fission rate distribution in each assembly converged in about 20 seconds (10 iterations) from the initial state. The axial fission rate distribution in each assembly is physically reasonable. These calculation results indicate that JAMPAN appropriately couples the neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations for the BWR whole core geometry.

Keywords: neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation, JAMPAN, MVP, NASCA, BWR, whole core

1. INTRODUCTION

The verification and validation of core design codes are very important for designing a new nuclear reactor and a nuclear fuel assembly. Large-scale mock-up test facilities are required for the validation of core design codes. However, many large-scale experimental facilities have already been closed. A huge amount of budget and long periods of time are required to construct and operate such a large-scale mock-up test facility. The requirement for such a large-scale facility increases the construction period and costs of a nuclear power plant. The reduction of mock-up tests is important to reduce the construction costs and accelerate the development of new nuclear reactors.

One effective way to reduce the number of mock-up tests is to utilize high-fidelity simulation results. High-fidelity simulation results will be an alternative to mock-up tests. Such high-fidelity multi-physics simulation results reveal detailed phenomena that cannot be observed in mock-up experiments, such as detailed void behavior above the control rod insertion region in BWRs. High-fidelity multi-physics simulation results are particularly required to verify core design codes for advanced reactors such as small modular reactors (SMRs) and micro reactors. These advanced reactors have very complex geometries and require highly accurate calculation results for their design. With the introduction of these advanced reactors, the demand for high-fidelity multi-physics simulation results has increased.

Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA) has developed high-fidelity single-physics calculation codes, such as continuous energy Monte Carlo calculation codes MVP [1] and the multiphase and multicomponent

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computational fluid dynamics code JUPITER [2]. However, JAEA has not developed a high-fidelity multi-physics calculation code.

JAEA is developing a high-fidelity multi-physics platform JAMPAN (JAEA Advanced Multi-Physics Analysis platform for Nuclear systems) [3-4]. JAMPAN is not a physics calculation code but is a platform to couple single-physics codes such as neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and fuel performance codes. This platform processes the output data of these single-physics codes and generates input files for them to perform multi-physics simulations. In our previous study, we demonstrated the neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation for a BWR single fuel assembly [3-4]. A single assembly geometry was calculated using MVP and the three-field subchannel code NASCA to verify the basic functions of JAMPAN, such as data transfer and input/output handling modules [3]. We also demonstrated a high-fidelity neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation using MVP and JUPITER [4]. This simulation can take into account details of void behavior in the fuel assembly. The temperature recovery method [5] was implemented in JUPITER to consider the phase change in gas-liquid two-phase flow.

In this study, we performed the BWR whole core neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation using MVP and NASCA. The inlet flow rate adjustment function was newly implemented to equalize the pressure loss among different assemblies. We modified the MVP input file generation function to set the control rod position and lattice geometry, *e.g.*, C- and D-lattices, to calculate a complex whole core geometry. The initial loading core of Peach Bottom Unit 2 obtained from the OECD/NEA Peach Bottom turbine trip benchmark [6] was used to verify the coupling simulation.

This paper provides an overview of the JAMPAN platform and shows the BWR whole core neutronics/thermal hydraulics coupling simulation results using this platform. This paper consists of 5 sections. Section 2 shows an overview of the JAMPAN platform. Section 3 shows a methodology and verification results of the inlet flow rate adjustment function to calculate multi-assembly BWR geometries. Section 4 shows the calculation of the BWR whole core neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation using this platform. Section 5 provides concluding remarks.

2. OVERVIEW OF JAMPAN

JAMPAN is a multi-physics platform to couple single-physics calculation codes. The concept of this platform is similar to other multi-physics platforms, such as MOOSE [7], ARMI [8], and SALOME [9] developed by INL, Terrapower, and CEA, respectively. This platform is written in Python 3. It does not require input files for operations. Users have to create Python scripts to run this platform. There are many sample scripts and explanations of classes and functions in the JAMPAN package. They can be useful for users to generate new scripts. Note that if users want to use a new assembly geometry, they will need to prepare basic input files corresponding to single physics codes.

JAMPAN is an open-source software under the 2-clause BSD license. Anyone can download the JAMPAN package from the JAEA website (https://rpg.jaea.go.jp/main/en/program_jampan/). Note that there is no single physics calculation function in this platform. Users have to prepare their own single-physics codes for running multi-physics simulations on this platform.

The latest version of JAMPAN can treat several single-physics calculation codes, including the neutronics code MVP; the thermal-hydraulics codes JUPITER, the three-dimensional two-fluid model analysis code ACE-3D [10], and NASCA [11]; and the fuel performance code FEMAXI [12]. At present, JAMPAN is applicable only to boiling water reactors (BWRs), while support for pressurized water reactors (PWRs) is planned for the near future. Furthermore, the extension of JAMPAN to simulations of advanced reactor concepts, such as very high-temperature gas-cooled reactors, is an important subject of our ongoing research. Since MVP is limited to steady-state calculations, the current version of JAMPAN is also restricted to steady-state analyses. The incorporation of other deterministic neutronics calculation codes to enable transient analyses is planned as future work. In addition to reactor core analyses, JAMPAN is expected to be applied to a wide range of engineering problems. As one such application, we are currently coupling a gas-liquid-solid three-phase flow calculation code with JAMPAN for criticality analysis during large-scale fuel debris retrieval operations at the Fukushima-Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant.

Figure 1 shows the system structure of JAMPAN. JAMPAN consists of the HDF5-formatted original data container and input and output handling modules. Users can easily change the calculation codes since the change of the calculation code only affects the input and output handling modules and has no impact on the data container. Users will be able to couple their own codes by adding the input and output handling modules for these codes. If users would like to add other single-physics, they will need to implement a new data container. For example, we implemented a fuel performance data container to couple with the fuel performance code FEMAXI.

Figure 1. System structure of JAMPAN.

3. INLET FLOW RATE ADJUSTMENT FUNCTION FOR BWR MULTI-ASSEMBLY GEOMETRY

NASCA is the thermal-hydraulics code for a single assembly. The inlet flow rate adjustment function is required to calculate the multi-assembly geometry. In this study, we used the following equation to adjust the inlet flow velocity of each assembly.

$$F_i = F_{i,j-1} + \left(1 - \frac{P_{i,j-1}}{P_{ave,j-1}}\right) f, \quad (1)$$

where, $F_{i,j}$ is the inlet flow velocity of each assembly [m/s], i is the assembly position, j is the number of iterations, $P_{i,j-1}$ is the inlet pressure of each assembly [MPa], $P_{ave,j-1}$ is the assembly average inlet pressure [MPa], and f is an adjustment factor. In our investigation, the neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling calculation converged when f is from 0.3 to 1.2. The default value of JAMPAN is $f = 0.6$. Note that the inlet pressure is largely changed at each time step. The time-averaged inlet pressure is used for $P_{i,j-1}$ and $P_{ave,j-1}$.

A 4×4 BWR fuel assembly geometry was simulated to verify the inlet flow rate adjustment function. As shown in Figure 2, the 9×9 fuel assembly obtained from the OECD/NEA Phase-3C benchmark [13] was used to represent a BWR assembly. Figure 3 shows the 4×4 BWR fuel assembly geometry. The values in Figure 3 represent the fuel assembly numbers (bxx) and their exposure [GWd/t]. These different exposure assembly data were used to consider the radial power distribution. The nuclide compositions of burn-up fuels were obtained from the burn-up calculations using the integrated burn-up code system SWAT-4 [14]. In this calculation, the interval between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations was 0.5 seconds, *i.e.*, a 0.5-second thermal-hydraulics calculation was performed between each neutronics calculation.

Figures 4 show the variation of the inlet flow velocity and inlet pressure at each time step. As shown in these figures, the inlet flow velocity and inlet pressure converged after 6 seconds (12 iterations). We also confirmed that the pressure loss among different assemblies reached almost the same value after 6 seconds. Figure 5 shows the variation of the k-infinity value at each time step. The k-infinity value also converged after 6 seconds. Comparing the convergence time of the single assembly geometry [3], the convergence time of the multi-assembly geometry is not significantly different. This result indicates that this adjustment function has no large impact on the convergence result. These results indicate that the inlet flow adjustment function in JAMPAN appropriately adjusts the inlet flow velocity to equalize the pressure loss among different assemblies.

Figure 2. Geometry of 9×9 fuel assembly.

				Reflective								
				b41	b42	b43	b44					
				(0)	(50)	(14)	(50)					
Reflective					b31	b32	b33	b34				
					(50)	(0)	(50)	(0)				
					b21	b22	b23	b24				
					(14)	(50)	(30)	(30)				
				b11	b12	b13	b14					
				(50)	(0)	(30)	(30)					
				Reflective								

Figure 3. Exposure distribution [GWd/t] of 4×4 fuel assembly geometry.

Figure 4. Variation of inlet flow velocity and inlet pressure at each time step.

Figure 5. Variation of k-infinity at each time step.

4. BWR WHOLE CORE NEUTRONICS/THERMAL-HYDRAULICS SIMULATION

A BWR whole core neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation using JAMPAN was performed to verify this platform. The initial loading core of Peach Bottom Unit 2 obtained from the OECD/NEA Peach Bottom turbine trip benchmark was used for this simulation. Figure 6 shows the 1/4 BWR core, and 7×7 and 8×8 fuel assemblies used in this benchmark. Details of the geometry and fuel compositions are described in Reference 6. As shown in this figure, Peach Bottom Unit 2 uses 7×7 fuel assemblies. The previous version of JAMPAN only handled 8×8 and 9×9 fuel assemblies. We have improved JAMPAN to handle these assemblies. Note that this calculation does not consider spacers in the fuel assembly. The handling of the spacers in JAMPAN is our future work.

The calculation conditions are shown in Table I. The interval in this table indicates that the neutronics calculation using MVP was performed after a 2-second thermal-hydraulics calculation using NASCA. The average inlet flow velocity is 2.1537 m/s, and the axial length of this core is 3.6576 m. The thermal-hydraulics calculation almost reached a steady state after 2 seconds since the bottom of the water passes the top of the fuel after 2 seconds. The average assembly power and the average inlet flow velocity shown in this table were used as the initial values for all assemblies. The 0% void distribution, that is, no vapor, was used as the initial condition. In this study, the number of particle histories per batch was set to 13,000. Although this number is not sufficient to achieve fully converged results for the whole core geometry, it was selected as a compromise between statistical accuracy and computational cost in order to complete the calculations within a few months.

Figure 7 shows the variation of k-effective at each time step. The statistical uncertainty of k-effective values is 0.018%. As shown in this figure, the k-effective value converged around 20 seconds (10 iterations). The converged k-effective value is slightly lower than one. The cause of this difference is not found. The lack of spacer consideration and the small number of histories may have affected the slightly lower k-effective value. Figure 8 shows the axial fission rate distribution for selected fuel assemblies and the core average axial void distribution at each time step. The selected assembly locations are shown in Figure 6. The peak position was moved from the top to the bottom. The convergence speed varied for each assembly. In these three assemblies, the convergence speed of the center assembly (Assembly position A) was slower than that of the other assemblies. The axial power distributions for all assemblies at 22 seconds (11 iterations) were almost flat. This result indicates that the converged results are physically reasonable. These results demonstrate that JAMPAN appropriately couples neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations.

Figure 6. 1/4 BWR core and fuel assembly geometries of Peach Bottom Unit 2.

Table I. Calculation conditions of BWR core simulation.

General	Average assembly power	4.0947 [MW]
	Pressure	7.2 [MPa]
	Inlet temperature	279.833 [°C]
	Average inlet flow velocity	2.1537 [m/s]
	Number of axial nodes	24
	Axial node length	15.24 [cm]
	Interval between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculation	2 [s]
MVP	Total number of histories	13,000,000
	Number of histories in each batch	13,000
	Number of batches	1,100
	Number of skip batches	100
NASCA	Evaluated nuclear data library	JENDL-4.0
	Number of sub-regions in a subchannel	1
	Time step	0.02 [ms]
	Gap thermal conductivity	0.5 [W/mK]

 Figure 7. Variation of k -effective at each time step.

Figure 8. Axial fission rate distributions of the selected fuel assemblies and core average axial void distribution at each time step.

5. CONCLUSIONS

JAEA is developing the high-fidelity multi-physics platform JAMPAN to provide verification results for core design codes. Calculation data of each single-physics code are stored in the HDF5-formatted original data container. These data are independent of the single physics codes. The change of the calculation code only affects the input and output handling modules and has no impact on the data container. This allows users to easily couple and change single-physics codes. This platform is an open-source software under the 2-clause BSD license. Anyone can download the JAMPAN package from the JAEA website. This platform does not include any single physics calculation function. Users have to prepare their own single-physics codes for running the multi-physics simulation on this platform.

In this study, several functions, such as the inlet flow adjustment function, were developed to calculate BWR multi-assembly geometry, including whole core geometry, using MVP/NASCA coupling simulations. The inlet flow velocity of each assembly was modified using the previous time step and the average inlet pressure. A 4×4 BWR fuel assembly geometry consisting of different burn-up fuel assemblies was simulated to verify the adjustment function. It was confirmed that the inlet flow velocity, inlet pressure, and pressure loss among different assemblies appropriately converged using this method. The calculation results also indicated that this adjustment function has no large impact on the convergence of the neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation.

The 1/4 BWR core neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation using JAMPAN was performed to verify this platform. The initial loading core of Peach Bottom Unit 2 obtained from the OECD/NEA Peach Bottom turbine trip benchmark was used for a BWR whole core simulation. The k -effective value and axial power distribution converged around 20 seconds. The axial power distributions in the selected assemblies were physically reasonable. These results indicate that JAMPAN appropriately couples neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations.

There are many development issues to improve the JAMPAN platform. For example, handling the PWR-type reactors and the consideration of spacers in a fuel assembly. These issues are currently being addressed. JAMPAN is expected to be used for many purposes. We are now combining a gas-liquid-

solid three-phase flow calculation code for criticality analysis during the large-scale fuel debris retrieval in the Fukushima-Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant.

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